

Eco-Friendly Pavement Solutions: Geopolymer Concrete with Recycled Aggregates and Geobead Fillers

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Abstract: Utilizing construction or mining waste as an alternative material is one of the efforts to overcome environmental problems. One of the recycled materials from these activities is structural concrete demolition and fly ash (FA) from burning coal in power plants. This research aims to develop and analyze the feasibility of using modified materials derived from recycled products, namely recycled concrete waste (RCA) in the sand gradation range, fly ash, and geobead, with the polymerization process. This research also finds a combination of FA, GB, and alkaline activator to fulfill the standard as a lightweight pavement in the base and subbase layer. The research method used was testing the physical and mechanical properties before and after stabilization with geopolymer. The mechanical parameter that is the focus of this research is compressive strength, which is compared with applicable regulations. According to ASTM, AASHTO, and Indonesian Code, utilization of RCA from structural concrete waste meets the requirements as a lightweight pavement on subbase layer, base layer, or as a concrete asphalt mix. A combination of RCA-Geobead stabilized with geopolymer is feasible to be used as an alternative lightweight material in the base layer and subbase layer with a seven-day curing time.

Keywords: geobead; geopolymer; lightweight fill; recycled concrete aggregate; road pavement

1. Introduction

Sustainable development is the main objective in addressing environmental issues. Efforts can be made to reduce the excessive use of natural resources. The most common granular materials used in the construction sector are embankments, retaining walls, sub-base layer, and railway ballast¹. One way to overcome the huge demand for soil fill material, as well as aggregates is to utilize waste materials from the mining industry, fossil or coal combustion, and demolition from the construction industry such as recycled concrete aggregate (RCA)^{1,2,3}, recycled glass aggregate (RGA)^{4,5,6}, tire derived aggregate/tire chip (TDA)^{7,8,9}, reclaimed asphalt pavement (RPA)^{10,11}, or a combination of these materials. These materials have the potential to be used in large quantities as structural fill in highway embankments, retaining walls, and road pavement¹². The limiting barriers to the use of RCA are the lack of information and the lack of understanding of RCA, as well as the limited regulations related to the use of RCA¹³. Recycled concrete aggregates have different characteristics depending on their constituents. In general, RCA consists of mortar that adheres to the surface of the rock so that it closes the available pores in the rock¹⁴.

Porosity limitation will result in increased pavement strength. However, a higher percentage of mortar will result in a lighter embankment condition as mortar is highly porous and less dense than natural aggregate (NA)¹⁵.

RCA is classified as GP, GW, GM, SP based on grain analysis^{16,17}. The particle size distribution depends on the material used in the construction, the technique used to demolish the building, and the number of crushers used to recycle the material³. In addition, RCA has a relatively high total absorption value in the range of 4% - 6%. It also has a specific gravity range of 1.20 - 2.60^{13,15}. Other research included Los Angeles (LA) crushing and abrasion tests. These tests were conducted to determine the durability of the aggregates and to show the percentage of mass loss due to the impact of steel balls. The results of these tests showed that the mass loss of RCA was 10%-60% and the mass loss of NA was 10%-40%. This shows that the mass loss of RCA is greater than that of NA because the steel balls produce fine particles and leave a small residue of mortar and flattening¹⁵.

Some mechanical properties of RCA were also tested, namely flexural strength test and the compressive strength test. Based on the results of several tests, it was found that

the compressive strength value of RCA is lower than the compressive strength of NA, and the value of elasticity modulus of RCA is smaller than NA¹⁸). Based on several tests of mechanical parameters that have been conducted, the results show that RCA qualifies as an embankment and pavement layer. Although some results show poor performance. Efforts can be made to improve the performance and durability by stabilization^{19),20)}. One of the eco-friendly stabilization methods that utilizes waste materials by using geopolymers.

In the 1980s, a new binder material, geopolymer (GP), was discovered as a replacement for ordinary Portland cement. The material is made from by-products such as fly ash, slag, rice husk ash, metakaolin, and other alkaline materials²¹⁾. Fly ash is a precursor material used as a geopolymer gelling agent along with an alkaline activator. The material is derived from the combustion of coal in power plants. The result of the combustion is used to stabilize the soil through a polymerization process²²⁾.

Experts have researched FA-based geopolymers to determine their composition, strength, and durability for long-term use. The studies conducted by Odeh & Al-Rkaby. (2022), which aimed to investigate the effects of fly ash ratio, activator to fly ash ratio, and clay content. The results of the study concluded that the use of geopolymers based on high calcium type C fly ash significantly increased the unconfined compressive strength values for all activator ratios, and the geopolymer-stabilized samples showed high durability against acidic and alkaline environments. For low fly ash content, the decrease in UCS did not exceed 10% and 38% against chloride (NaCl) and acid (H₂SO₄), respectively²³⁾.

The study was conducted by Liang & Ji. (2021) revealed that the use of geopolymer concrete can be used as a material to support structures. Geopolymer concrete also has a permeability coefficient value 3.1 times lower than conventional concrete²⁴⁾. Tiyasangthong et al. (2022) conducted a study on RCA stabilized using geopolymer-based fly ash as the base layer. It was found that the use of RCA-based GP was able to improve the performance of the base layer on roads with low to high traffic volumes compared to conventional stabilizers. Increasing the level of FA as a binder material also contributes to an increase in the compressive strength value up to 3 times compared to without using FA²⁰⁾.

However, in practice, the use of concrete aggregate material as a base layer has the disadvantage that it has a large enough density to cause an increase in the overburden pressure on the original soil layer (subgrade) under the base layer¹³⁾. One way to reduce the weight of the contents in the RCA material is to add Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) Bead or Geobead as an inclusion material. Geobead is a derivative of expanded polystyrene material in granular form. The smaller size of the EPS bead is very useful to improve the shear parameters and bearing capacity of the

soil. It also provides good control of compression and yielding in serviceability due to its low heat transfer coefficient and flexibility. EPS is also classified as plastic foam with several advantages such as light weight, compression resistance, durability, and thermal insulation. Thus, in its utilization, it is often used in construction engineering²⁵⁾. The absorbency of EPS is also relatively low. The absorbency of EPS decreases as the size of the material increases²⁶⁾.

The addition of EPS has a significant effect in reducing the density, thus reducing the overburden pressure on the underlying original soil²⁷⁾. Research conducted by Charisma et al. (2021) shows that the use of EPS Bead reduces the overburden pressure due to the soil's weight by up to 22.50%, and the percentage of geobead addition reduces the permeability coefficient and CBR values²⁷⁾. In addition, research conducted by Zaika et al. (2023) found that the use of EPS reduces the potential for settlement and collapse on steep slope embankments²⁸⁾.

The main alternative material used as a pavement layer is recycled concrete aggregate stabilized with geopolymer (GP). The material comes from building demolition. In-situ crushing is a simple method of recycling concrete²⁹⁾. The waste has been used as a base course, subbase, backfill, and by-product material. However, the application is still limited. This research aims to develop an innovative pavement material by utilizing recycled and industrial by-products, specifically recycled concrete aggregate (RCA) in sand range gradation, fly ash, and geobeads through a geopolymerization process. The goal is to engineer a sustainable and high-performance composite material that not only reduces dependence on natural aggregates but also promotes environmental responsibility by repurposing construction and industrial waste. By leveraging the chemical bonding and structural properties offered by the geopolymerization reaction, this study seeks to enhance the mechanical performance and durability of pavement structures while contributing to circular economy principles in civil engineering. Tests conducted include sieve analysis, standard compaction, xray fluorescence, Los Angeles aggregate abrasion test, unconfined compressive strength (UCS) by comparing the variations in the amount of geobead in each RCA and FA mixture, and determining the appropriate composition for alternative lightweight pavement materials in based and subbased layer based on applicable Indonesian national standards.

2. Methodology

2.1. Material Collection and Preparation

2.1.1. Recycled Concrete Aggregate

In this study, the components and composition of the alternative pavement in the base and subbase layer were

based on previous research. The main material used as the road pavement is recycled concrete aggregate³⁰. The material is obtained from the demolition of structural concrete buildings, then it is crushed with a stone crusher until it has the size of sand, with the criteria of passing through the No. 4 sieve³¹.

2.1.2. Geobead

Another substitute material is Geobeads (GB), which are derived from expanded polystyrene (EPS) derivatives in granular form. This material is generally 4 - 6 mm in size²⁷. Based on the content weight test using a 4" PVC pipe, the volume weight of Geobeads is 0.007203 g/cm³. The shape of the Geobead is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Geobead

2.1.3. Fly Ash

Fly ash (FA) is the waste product of coal combustion in power plants and petrochemical industries. The composition of the material depends on the mineral characteristics of the coal and the combustion conditions²². In general, a product of coal combustion or fly ash is divided into three types, namely C-type, F-type, and N-type³². The difference between types of fly ash lies in the constituent elements and compounds in fly ash required by ASTM C618, as shown in Table 1. The function of fly ash in geopolymers is as a precursor, where the material is the main ingredient in the polymerization process. The silica and alumina atoms react with the alkaline activator to form a geopolymer network or gel that hardens like naturally formed rock³³.

Table 1: Chemical requirement (ASTM C618)

Parameter	Class		
	N	F	C
SiO ₂ + Al ₂ O ₃ + Fe ₂ O ₃ , %	70	50	50
CaO, %	-	18	> 18
SO ₃ , %	4	5	5
Moisture content, max%	3	3	3
Loss on ignition, max%	10	6	6

2.1.4. Alkaline Activator Solution

Activators are alkaline materials used to break silica (Si) and alumina (Al) atoms from inorganic precursors and catalysts for condensation reactions²². Several types of alkaline activators can be used as polymer formers. However, in this research, the alkaline activators used are NaOH and Na₂SiO₃ because they have a relatively lower cost compared to other alkaline activators³⁴.

2.2. Mix Design of Geopolymer Composite

Geopolymers are bonding systems that generally cure at room temperature. Different types of geopolymer components have been studied previously. However, in this study, the binder material used is high calcium fly ash (FA) or FA type C. In general, high calcium fly ash (type C) has several advantages, including shorter setting time, increased degree of hydration at early ages, and does not require hot curing temperatures for hardening and strength improvement³⁵. With percentage variations of 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40% following the research of Odeh & Al-Rkaby. (2022) and Sahoo & Singh. (2022)^{21,23}. Based on the research of Odeh & Al-Rkaby. (2022), the activators (AC) used are sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and sodium silicate (Na₂SiO₃) at a concentration of 10M each²³, and the ratio of alkaline activator (AC) to precursor (FA) is 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0²³. The mass ratios of (NaOH) and silica (Na₂SiO₃) used were 1:1, 1:2, 4:6, and 3:7. The NaOH was dissolved for 24 hours before the Na₂SiO₃ solution was added³⁶.

The trial mixture was prepared to determine the ideal composition between the AC/FA ratio and the NaOH/Na₂SiO₃ solution ratio to be used as the activator of RCA, FA, and GB. The AC/FA ratio was determined based on the weight of NaOH+Na₂SiO₃ solution compared to the weight of FA. The performance evaluated in this test is the initial setting time of the mix as well as the unconfined compressive strength value with 1 day curing. AC solution with a ratio of (1:1) is mixed with FA with AC/FA ratios of 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, and 1.0, respectively, to form 4 specimens. Then AC solution with a ratio of (1:2) was mixed with FA with AC/FA ratios of 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, and 1.0, respectively, to form 4 specimens. Furthermore, the AC solution with a ratio of (4:6) is mixed with FA with AC/FA ratios of 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, and 1.0, respectively, to form 4 specimens. And the last AC solution with a ratio of (3:7) mixed with FA with AC/FA ratios of 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, and 1.0, respectively, to form 4 specimens. The number of specimens made was 16, with 4 variations of the AC/FA ratio and 4 variations of the NaOH/Na₂SiO₃ ratio. The determination of the solution ratio is based on the maximum compressive strength value and the optimum

initial setting time. The detail of the Trial mix sequence is shown in Figure 2. The combination of activator ratios is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Combinations of solutions

AC/FA NaOH/Na ₂ SiO ₃	0,4	0,6	0,8	1,0
1:1	√	√	√	√
1:2	√	√	√	√
4:6	√	√	√	√
3:7	√	√	√	√

2.3. Sample Preparation

In this study, a series of 4 compressive strength test specimens were prepared with varying levels of geobead addition. The GB addition concentrations used were 20%, 30%, and 40%, which were determined from the ratio of specimen volume. Meanwhile, the amount of FA precursor was 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40%, which were determined from the ratio of the dry weight of the soil. The experimental matrix for the entire test is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Research matrix

No	Specimens Code	% GB	% FA
1	FA - XRF		√
2	RCA - abrasion		
3	FA - Trial mix	√	√

No	Specimens Code	% GB	% FA
4	FA10 - C		10%
5	FA20 - C		20%
6	FA30 - C		30%
7	FA40 - C		40%
8	GB0 - C	0%	√
9	GB20 - C	20%	√
10	GB30 - C	30%	√
11	GB40 - C	40%	√
12	GB0 - UCS	0%	√
13	GB20 - UCS	20%	√
14	GB30 - UCS	30%	√
15	GB40 - UCS	40%	√

The activator consists of two different alkaline base solutions, NaOH and Na₂SiO₃. The solution was prepared with a concentration of 10M each and let it sit for 24 hours³⁶. According to the specified ratio, the NaOH and Na₂SiO₃ were mixed and stirred for 5 minutes, then left at room temperature for 5-10 minutes³⁶. The soil, FA, and geobeads were mixed and stirred for approximately 3 minutes until well mixed. To achieve the desired moisture content, the alkaline solution was mixed with water and then gradually added to the dry material mixture. The materials were then stirred until a homogeneous mixture was obtained.

Fig. 2: Mix order of the trial mix test

2.4. Mechanical Testing

2.4.1. Los Angeles Test

This test is based on ASTM C131. The equipment required for this test consists of a Los Angeles machine and solid steel balls. Generally, this test is performed as a parameter to measure the aggregate degradation caused by the impact of the steel balls on the aggregate.

2.4.2. Dry density

The test is based on ASTM D698. The standard compaction method performed was a mixture of RCA with several variations in FA percentage. After that, the highest MDD value was obtained for further standard compaction with the addition of geobeads. Geobeads were added to the optimum FA mix condition, and standard compaction was performed to obtain the final MDD (maximum dry density) and OMC (optimum moisture content) values as the basis for making UCS test specimens and density control.

2.4.3. Compressive Strength Test

The purpose of the Compressive Strength Test is to determine the value of unconfined compressive strength of cohesive or cemented soils in undisturbed, remoulded, or compacted conditions using strain measurements associated with axial loads based on ASTM D2166 standards. The result of this test is a compressive strength value. The compressive strength specimen is made in the shape of a cube. The specimen is placed between the load plates and then loaded at a constant speed. The compressive strength testing configuration is depicted in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Testing setup of the compressive strength test

2.5. Microstructural Analyses

X-ray fluorescence analysis (XRF) is a widely used method for estimating the geochemical composition of rock, sediment, and soil samples. This test is considered to be the most effective method because of its ability to quickly determine the oxidic elemental composition of various earth materials such as granules, powders, or solid powders. The working mechanism of XRF is based on the principle of wavelength dispersion, which states that individual atoms emit relatively abundant X-ray photons with predictable energy or wavelength characteristics. The result of this test is the elemental content of the raw material in the form of a percentage or ppm (parts per million)³⁷.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Physical Properties of Geopolymer Composite

3.1.1. Properties of RCA

In this study, samples for structural concrete without mixing other materials with an age of more than 28 days were used. The RCA used is the sand range obtained from crushed waste concrete, as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: RCA Material

Several tests were conducted to determine the characteristics of the material of RCA^{30,38}. The coarse and medium sand ranges dominate the aggregate size, while the fine sand size is only about 15%, as shown in Figure 5. Based on the grain size distribution analysis, it is known that RCA meets the requirements of base and subbase layer gradation depend on ASTM D2940 standard with characteristics of grain size smaller than 37.5 mm, passing sieve 200 smaller than 8%, and having PI smaller than 6%.

Fig. 5: Particle size distribution of RCA

The test results are displayed in Table 4. A view of the RCA chunks to sand passing the #4 sieve is shown in Figure 5.

Table 4: Physical properties of RCA

Soil Characteristics	Unit	Value
Specific Gravity	-	2.45
Water Content SSD	%	8.36

Soil Characteristics	Unit	Value
Optimum Water Content	%	24.43
Unit Weight	kN/m ³	16.11
D ₁₀		0.400
D ₃₀		2.138
D ₆₀		3.257
C _u		8.143
C _c		3.507

The result of the LA Abrasion Test is the percentage of loss of mass aggregate obtained from the weight of aggregate passing through the #12 sieve. The test results are shown in Table 5.

Fig. 6: Material and steel ball for abrasion test

Table 5: Los Angeles result

Weight specimen (g)	(A)	5000
Weight retained on the 12 sieve (g)	(B)	3298.5
Percentage of wear (%)	(A-B)/A * 100%	34

Based on the ASTM D692, the coarse aggregate derived from recycled structural concrete material is suitable for the base layer in low traffic and sub-base layer, even for high traffic, due to its layer with a maximum wear value of 40% as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Typical specification limit based on ASTM

Layer type	LA Abrasion Limit (%)	Remark
Base layer (high quality)	< 30 - 35	High traffic load
Sub-base layer	< 40 -45	Slightly Lower quality aggregate
Unpaved road/ low traffic	< 50	Permissible rural with low load demand
RCA	< 40 -50	Depending on the national local code

According to the 2018 General Specifications for Road and Bridge Construction Works, Directorate General of Highways, Ministry of Public Works and Housing (KEMENPUPR, Bina Marga), and in the aggregate base layer with a maximum wear value of 40%³⁹.

The RCA is suitable for filler material in asphalt patching

applications as a crack or pothole filler with a maximum wear value of 40%. However, according to AASHTO M325-2012 and KEMENPUPR General Specifications, the use of RCA is not recommended for Modified Asphalt Concrete (MAC) and Stone Matrix Asphalt (SMA) mixes, because of the maximum wear value of 30% for 500 revolutions⁴⁰. However, RCA can be used in many other types of graded pavement mixes³⁹.

Figure 6 show RCA and steel ball inside Los Angeles abrasion machine and Figure 7 shows that the RCA has an angular shape with an overall rough surface. The test produced the fine particles shown in Figure 8 and left residual mortar and small cracks on the aggregate surface. The particle shape and surface roughness affected the resistance and shear strength of the aggregate. Compared to the spherical particles, the angular RCA was advantageous in reducing permanent deformation⁴¹.

Fig. 7: Retained RCA from No.12 sieve

Fig. 8: Passed RCA from No.12 sieve

3.1.2. Fly Ash Composition

The classification of fly ash types based on elemental chemical content by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis is shown in Table 7 of compound and Table 8 of element. Spectra of fly ash provides information on the major and trace elements present in fly ash as Figure 9.

Table 7: Composition of fly ash compounds

Compound	Value (%)
Al ₂ O ₃	9.7
SiO ₂	27.2
SO ₃	1.0

Compound	Value (%)
K ₂ O	1.42
CaO	26.4
TiO ₂	1.31
V ₂ O ₅	0.06
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.087
MnO	0.43
Fe ₂ O ₃	28.9
NiO	0.04
CuO	0.056

Table 8: Composition of fly ash elements

Element	Value (%)
Al	7.0
Si	17.8
S	0.59
K	1.82
Ca	30.0
Ti	1.32
V	0.06
Cr	0.10
Mn	0.58
Fe	35.9
Ni	0.06
Cu	0.083
Zn	0.02
Sr	1.6
Zr	0.3
Ba	0.78
Eu	0.49
Yb	0.04
Re	0.2
Hg	0.31

formation process of cementation products. The high presence of calcium in C-type FA can modify the microstructure and the polymerization process³⁴. While the application of F-type FA is energy efficient and environmentally friendly, the application of F-type FA has an impact on the need for high curing temperatures and large amounts of alkaline activators²³.

3.1.3. Optimum Alkali Activator Solution

Based on the test mix experiment, unconfined compressive strength results were obtained, which are used to determine the alkali activator content in the geopolymerization process. The results of this test are presented in Table 9 and Table 10.

Table 9: UCS value of the trial mix

AC/FA	Strength (MPa)	AC/FA	Strength (MPa)
0.4 (1:1)	1.27	0.8 (1:1)	0.94
0.4 (1:2)	0.95	0.8 (1:2)	0.64
0.4 (4:6)	0.92	0.8 (4:6)	0.58
0.4 (3:7)	0.54	0.8 (3:7)	0.43
0.6 (1:1)	1.00	1.0 (1:1)	0.43
0.6 (1:2)	0.99	1.0 (1:2)	0.42
0.6 (4:6)	0.73	1.0 (4:6)	0.36
0.6 (3:7)	0.59	1.0 (3:7)	0.16

Table 10: Initial setting time of the trial mix

AC/FA	Setting Time (min)	AC/FA	Setting Time (min)
0.4 (1:1)	4	0.8 (1:1)	10
0.4 (1:2)	6	0.8 (1:2)	12
0.4 (4:6)	8	0.8 (4:6)	18
0.4 (3:7)	6	0.8 (3:7)	12
0.6 (1:1)	8	1.0 (1:1)	16
0.6 (1:2)	10	1.0 (1:2)	26
0.6 (4:6)	12	1.0 (4:6)	18
0.6 (3:7)	8	1.0 (3:7)	24

Fig. 9: Spectra XRF of fly ash

Based on the XRF test, the results show that the content of Al₂O₃, SiO₂, Fe₂O₃ compounds is 9.7%, 27.2%, and 28.9%, respectively. And the Ca content in FA is 30%. The sum of Al₂O₃, SiO₂ and Fe₂O₃ is 65.8%. Therefore, according to ASTM C618, it is known that the material belongs to the category of FA type C because the Ca content is more than 18% and the amount of Al₂O₃ + SiO₂ + Fe₂O₃ is more than 50%. The difference between FA types C and F lies in the amount of alumina-silica and calcium, which influence the

The highest compressive strength value occurred at a ratio of 0.4 (1:1) with a value of 1.27 MPa. Meanwhile, the lowest compressive strength value occurred at a solution ratio of 1.0 (3:7). However, the level of alkaline activator solution used in this study was 0.6 (1:2), where the value was 0.6 for AC/FA and 1:2 for NaOH/Na₂SiO₃. This is due to the consideration of the initial setting time with a duration of 10 minutes, which allows for the process of mixing raw materials and forming specimens for testing.

3.1.4. Dry Density of Geopolymer Composite in Variation of FA

Standard compaction was used to determine the maximum dry density and optimum moisture content of the soil and fly ash mixture. The results of this test are presented in Figure 10 and Figure 11.

Fig. 10: Optimum moisture content of the Maximum dry density of Geopolymer composite in the variation of FA

Fig. 12: Optimum moisture content of geopolymer composite

Fig. 11: Maximum dry density of Geopolymer composite in the variation of FA

Fig. 13: Maximum dry density of geopolymer composite

Based on the results of standard compaction tests of RCA and FA mixture. It is found that there is an increase in the maximum dry density (MDD) value as the percentage of FA increases. Meanwhile, the optimum moisture content (OMC) value decreased as the percentage of FA increased. The largest MDD value occurred with the addition of 40% FA, namely 19.12 kN/m³. And the lowest MDD value occurs with the addition of 10% FA, which is 16.69 kN/m³. In contrast to MDD, the highest OMC value occurs with the addition of 10% FA, namely 18.56%. The lowest OMC value occurs with the addition of 40% FA, which is 13.06%. The 40% FA content is the optimum amount that will be used in further research with the addition of geobeads.

3.1.5. Dry Density of Geopolymer Composite

Standard compaction was used to determine the maximum content weight and optimum moisture content of the soil, fly ash, and geobead mixture. The results of this test are shown in Figure 12 and Figure 13.

Based on the results of standard compaction tests of RCA, FA, and Geobead mixture. It is found that there is a decrease in the maximum density (MDD) value as the percentage of Geobead increases. The lowest MDD value occurs with the addition of 40% Geobead at 16.7 kN/m³. Meanwhile, the optimum moisture content (OMC) value increased as the percentage of geobead increased. The highest OMC value occurred with the addition of 40% Geobead at 14.13%. However, there was a decrease in OMC with the addition of 30% geobead, which was 12.74%. The results of this standard compaction will be used as a basis for determining the amount of activator used in the production of UCS test specimens.

3.2. Compressive Strength of Specimen

The compressive strength test specimens were formed using a square mould of 15cm x 15cm x 15cm, with a curing time of 1 to 7 days and geobead additions of 0%, 20%, 30%, and 40%. The results of the unconfined compressive strength test with cure periods of 1 and 7 days are shown in Table 11 and Table 12. Meanwhile, Figure 15 shows a comparison of compressive strength values with varying curing times.

Table 11: Compressive strength and density of geopolymer composite in 1 day

Amount of geobead (%)	Specimen weight(kg)	Density (kN/m ³)	Strength (MPa)
0	7.52	22.28	10.71
20	6.42	19.02	3.96
30	6.02	17.84	2.53
40	5.66	16.77	1.87

Table 12: Compressive strength test and density of geopolymer composite in 7 days

Amount of geobead (%)	Specimen weight (kg)	Density (kN/m ³)	Strength (MPa)
0	7.62	22.58	20.00
20	6.64	19.67	9.60
30	6.12	18.13	8.71
40	5.19	15.38	5.56

Fig. 14: Compressive strength of geopolymer composite

Based on the results (Figure 14) of the unconfined compressive strength test with a one-day curing time, the specimen without geobead had the maximum compressive strength, 10.71MPa. The specimen with 40% geobead had the lowest compressive strength, at 1.87 MPa. Meanwhile, the unconfined compressive strength test with a 7-day curing time indicated that the specimen without geobead had the maximum compressive strength of 20.00 MPa. The specimen with 40% geobead addition had the lowest compressive strength, at a stress of 5.5 MPa.

In general, the compressive strength increased with fly ash content up to a point, but excessive geobead replacement beyond 82.5% caused a significant drop due to reduced particle interlocking. By increasing the curing time by 7 days, the decrease in strength becomes smaller at 14.5%. The increase in strength occurred due to the coexistence of calcium silicate hydrate (CSH) and geopolymer gel, resulting from NaOH continuously leaching alumina and silica from FA2. Figure 15 shows the relationship between increasing curing time duration and compressive strength values.

The experiment revealed that the use of geopolymer-based FA with a percentage of 40%, an AC/FA ratio of 0.6, and

NaOH: Na₂SiO₃ ratio = 1:2 has a faster bonding time compared to foam mortar materials. This is evidenced by the compressive strength value of geopolymer specimens with a curing duration of 1 day is greater than the compressive strength of foam mortar specimens with a curing duration requirement of 7 days.

Fig. 15: Influence of curing time on compressive strength of geopolymer composite

Tiyasangthong et al. (2022) examined the effect of FA content on compressive strength values. In this study, the FA content used was 30%. The largest compressive strength value occurred with a curing duration of 7 days, namely 16.42 MPa. The compressive strength of specimens with 40% FA content shows a greater value than the compressive strength of specimens with 30% FA content. Increasing the level of FA content increases the compressive strength value. This is due to the increase in FA content forming a denser geopolymer matrix²⁰. Comparison of the effect of compressive strength on the duration of curing time is shown in Figure 15.

According to AASHTO and the Technical Planning of Lightweight Foamed Mortar Backfill Material for Road Construction, Ministry of Public Works and Housing, 2015, the required strength for sub-base and base layer is shown in Table 13. In the case of geopolymer composite application, it must meet the requirements of sub-base and base stabilization. This condition is only met with 40% geobead content with 7 days curing or with 30% geobead content with more than 1 day curing.

Table 13: Typical strength requirement

Layer	Parameter	Requirement
Sub base (granular)	CBR (unsoaked)	≥20%
Base (granular)	CBR (unsoaked)	≥80%
Sub base (stabilized)	UCS	1.5 MPa
Base (stabilized)	UCS	2.1 – 3 MPa
Sub Base *	UCS	0.80 MPa
Base *	UCS	2.00 MPa

*Ministry of Public Works and Housing, Indonesia⁴²

The RCA-geobead-based geopolymer mix with 1 day curing time and all variations of geobead addition are suitable for use as the subbase layer of the road because it has a compressive strength value of $>0.80 \text{ MPa}$ ⁴²⁾. Geopolymer material with 40% geobead content for a 1-day curing time does not qualify as the base layer of road construction because it has a compressive strength value below the standard.

According to Table 4, the RCA density is 16.11 kN/m^3 , which is lower than the soil fill. The density decreased after the polymer reaction in 7 days, reaching 16.77 kN/m^3 for the mixture without geobeads and 15.38 kN/m^3 (average value) with 40% geobead content after 1 and 7 days.

Fig. 16: Failure pattern of geopolymer specimen

Figure 16 shows the failure pattern of the compressive strength test. The geopolymer composite of RCA without geobead exhibits stiff material collapse, which occurs when the material is unable to bear a compressive load greater than its compressive strength limit, resulting in rupture or fracture. While the geopolymer composites of RCA with geobeads displayed uneven collapse, all planes fell due to the geobead connection with other materials.

4. Conclusion

This research observed the physical and mechanical behaviour of recycled concrete aggregate with the addition of geobead stabilised with fly ash-based geopolymer. The result of this research is an ideal composition between RCA, FA, and Geobead that is suitable for lightweight pavement material on the subbase layer and base layer. The conclusions from these tests include:

RCA materials in the coarse and medium range meet the criteria for good gradation and abrasion requirements for heavy loads for the sub-base layer and light loads for the base.

The fly ash used is type C, which ensures faster cementation of the material because it has a high CaO content.

The addition of geobead to the geopolymer composite mix decreased the dry density from 19.3 kN/m^3 with 40% fly ash C type (weight ratio) to 16.7 kN/m^3 for the same fly ash content with 40% geobead added (volume ratio).

The curing time has a substantial effect, with an 82.5% decrease in strength in 1 day at 40% geobead content, but only a 14.5% decline after 7 days of curing compare to without geobead.

According to ASTM D692, AASHTO M325-2012, and General Specifications for Road and Bridge Construction Works, Directorate General of Highways, Ministry of Public Works and Housing of the Republic of Indonesia (2018), the use of RCA from structural concrete waste meets the requirements as a lightweight pavement on subbase layer, base layer.

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